

The Criticism of Materialism in Late Ottoman's New Science of Kalām *

Mehmet Bulğen **

Abstract

Materialism, which reduces the whole of existence as simply matter and its interactions, and respectively ignores the intervention of a divine being into the universe; it is often traced back to a time when philosophy was born. However, when we study the historical process, we find that materialism was a thought that was generally rejected by the majority. With the enlightenment and secularism that came following the Renaissance, Reforms and 17th Century Scientific Revolution in Europe, materialism gained more followers. In the 20th century, in what was known as its golden era,

-
- * Previously published in Turkish: Mehmet Bulğen, "Osmanlı Yeni İlm-i Kelâmında Materyalizm Eleştirileri", *Bilimname: Düşünce Platformu* 30/1 (2016): 391-433.

I want to thank Zeliha Uluyurt for her contribution to the translation of the article into English.

- ** Associate Professor, Marmara University, Faculty of Theology, Department of Kalam, Istanbul, Turkey

Doç. Dr., Marmara Üniversitesi, İlahiyat Fakültesi, Kelam Anabilim Dalı

mbulgen@hotmail.com ORCID 0000-0002-2372-471X

Article Types: Translated Article

Received: 29 June 2019

Accepted: 31 July 2019

Published: 31 July 2019

Cite as: Mehmet Bulğen, "The Criticism of Materialism in Late Ottoman's New Science of Kalām", *ULUM* 2/1 (July 2019): 133-171, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3356845>

it became a world view by manifesting itself in the religious, social, political and economic spheres of life. Materialism came to the Ottomans following the first half of the 19th century through students who went to the West and newly established military and medical schools. Despite materialism forming the backbone of debates on westernization and secularism (perpetuating worldliness) towards the end of the 19th century, this did not deter many intellectuals from endorsing much of the values that came with materialism, and it led to many repercussions within the political and social realms of the Ottoman world. On the other hand, materialism was not welcomed but rather disapproved of by many Ottoman scholars of *kalām* (*mutakallimūn*) such as Abdullatif Harputi (1842-1916), İzmirli İsmail Hakkı (1868-1946), Mehmet Şemsettin Günaltay (1883-1961) and Ömer Nasûhi Bilmen (1882-1971). However, their criticism has caused them to break away from the classical period *mutakallimūn* in some respect. We attempt to outline the mentioned late period Ottoman *mutakallimūn*'s critique of materialism and compare their views with the classical *mutakallimūn*'s seemingly materialistic worldview.

Keywords

Kalām, Materialism, Ottomans, Atheism, New Kalām

Osmanlı Yeni İlm-i Kelâmında Materyalizm Eleştirileri

Öz

Bir bütün olarak varlığı madde ve etkileşimlerine indirgeyerek açıklayan, evreni kendisi dışındaki aşkın bir varlığın müdahalesine kapatan bir görüş olarak bilinen materyalizm, ortaya çıkış itibariyle felsefenin başlangıcına kadar gerilere götürülse de, tarihsel süreç içerisinde genelde azınlıkta kalan ve tepkiyle karşılanan bir düşünce olmuştur. Ancak bu görüş Avrupa’da XVII. Yüzyıl bilim devrimi ardından gelen aydınlanma ve sekülerleşme hadiseleri sonrasında yeniden taraftar bulmaya başlamış, XX. yüzyılın başlarına gelindiğinde altın çağını yaşayarak dinî, siyasî, ekonomik ve toplumsal tezahürleri de olan bir dünya görüşü haline gelmiştir. Materyalizmin Osmanlı’ya girişi ise XIX. yüzyılın ilk yarısından itibaren askerî ve tıp alanında açılan modern okullar ile Batı’ya eğitim amaçlı gönderilen öğrenciler vasıtasıyla başlamış; XIX. Yüzyılın sonlarında dünyevileşme, Batılılaşma gibi tartışmalara arka plan oluşturduğu halde önemli sayıda Osmanlı aydınını etkisi altına alarak siyasal ve toplumsal sonuçlara neden olmuştur. Diğer taraftan materyalizm Abdullatif Harpûtî (1842-1916), İzmirli İsmail Hakkı (1868-1946), M. Şemseddin Günaltay (1883-1961) ve Ömer Nasûhi Bilmen (1882-1971) gibi kelâmcıların da dâhil olduğu birçok Osmanlı ulemâsı tarafından tepkiyle karşılanarak eleştirilmiştir. Makalede söz konusu Osmanlı kelâmcılarının materyalizmi ne şekilde eleştirdikleri ve bu eleştirilerinde materyalistik imâlar taşıdığı söylenen klasik dönem kelâmından birleşip ayrıldıkları noktalar tespit edilmeye çalışılacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler

Kelâm, Materyalizm, Osmanlı, Yeni İlm-i Kelâm, Ateizm

INTRODUCTION

The approximately a century-long period from the Rescript of Gülhane in the Ottoman Empire (1839) until the foundation of the Republic (1923) is known as the most intense, painful and long century in the Ottoman history. In this period when there was dynamism and a search not only from military and political aspects, but also in ideational terms, Ottoman intellectuals discussed many issues with the concern of finding a solution to the negative conditions that the Empire was in.¹ Within these discussion topics, materialism has a special place not only because it is one of the anti-religious thought movements that emerged with the influence of Western thought, but also because it is seen as a prescription of salvation for the troubles experienced by the Ottoman Empire during the collapse period. Western-oriented intellectuals including Beşîr Fuâd (1852-1887), Bahâ Tevfik (1884-1914), Abdullah Cevdet (1869-1932), Celâl Nuri (1882-1936) and Kılıçzâde Hakkı (1872-1960) claimed that the level of contemporary civilizations would be attained if and only if the Muslim world adopted a materialist worldview, which is identified with science.²

On the other hand, the spreading of materialism in the Ottoman Empire towards the end of the 19th century brought with it the opposition of the traditionalist and conservative groups, who acted with the intention of defending their religious and cultural values. In this context, one of the groups that criticized materialism were the late Ottoman practitioners of *kalām* (i.e., *mutakallimūn*) including İsmail Hakkı İzmirli (1869-1946), Abdüllatîf Harpûti (1842-1916), Şehbenderzâde Ahmad Hilmi of Filibe (1865-1914), Ömer Nasûhi Bilmen (1882-1971) and M. Şemseddin Günaltay (1883- 1961).

However, the critique of materialism of Ottoman *mutakallimūn* is interesting in two respects. First, linking the science of *kalām* with materialism in a positive or negative sense requires sensitivity and attention because if materialism is to be criticized on the basis of spiritualism or idealism, then we will encounter classical Islamic theologians. As is known, the classical period *kalām* has a character expressed as “seemingly materialist”.³ This is due to the fact that the *kalām* in that period had a

¹ Süleyman Hayri Bolay, *Osmanlılarda Düşünce Hayatı ve Felsefe* (Ankara: Akçağ Yayınları 2005), 291-292.

² Aydın Topaloğlu, “Materyalizm”, *Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı İslam Ansiklopedisi* (İstanbul: TDV Yayınları, 2003), 28: 140; also see Ahmet İshak Demir, *Cumhuriyet Dönemi Aydınlarının İslâm’a Bakışı* (İstanbul: Ensar Neşriyat, 2004), 135 ff.

³ For the phrase “**seemingly materialist**” or “**even materialist**” (ve hatta materialist) that Prof. Dr. M. Saim Yeprem uses to describe the general character of the classical period *kalām* see. Şerife Akyol, *Materyalizmin İnsan Anlayışının Modern Çağın İnanç Problemleri Açısından Değerlendirilmesi* (Master Thesis, Marmara University, 2002), p. 10.